

THE ROLE OF BOBURNOMA IN FOREIGN TRANSLATION STUDIES

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Generations of people who have been living in different continents and regions of the earth for several thousand years have shown their creative passions, interests, opportunities through the medium of translation. It is turned into a means of international communication, which always used effectively. Through translation and translators, the peoples of mankind became aware of each other and communicated with each other. Uzbekistan's independent development, expansion of international relations, radical renewal of the country's educational processes, new requirements for personnel training, increased need for specialists - creation of contemporary and similar examples of translation theory manuals , to generalize and enlighten on a new point of view and scientific theoretical basis with colorful and very rich practical experience.

The importance of literary translation is immeasurable. It enables people to understand the world. Students are able to understand philosophy, politics and history through the translated works of Sophocles and Homer. Many more readers are able to enjoy new insights into the different ways of life through contemporary translations. More people are able to enjoy the creative, fertile and highly imaginative minds of foreign authors. Without the translation of literature, people would not be able to read the vast majority of literary works that are available in archives and libraries around the world. You would not be able to enjoy the ways ancient authors view the many facets of life and how they express their myriad emotions. You would not be able to understand how people back then think, compared to people who live in the modern era. Translation allows you to travel

back in time and relive such moments[1]. You are likewise given the chance to compare how things are done in the past and see some of the similarities as well as the changes that occur in the modern world. We will talk about the work ,which has been of equal interest to all peoples from history to the present day and has been translated into many languages, “Bobrunoma”.

An important and unique monument of world literature and source studies. It is written in the Old Uzbek (Chigatai) language. Numerous names of the work are also known, such as "Baburia", "Voqanoma", "Tuzuki Baburiy", "Tabagoti Baburiy", "Tavorihi Baburiy". A large source that tells in detail about the history of the Timurids. More than ten handwritten copies of the work are kept at the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. Translated into many secular languages, including Persian, English, Russian, Turkish, Dutch, French. In particular, the work was translated into Persian at the behest of Babur's grandson, the great ruler of Akbarshah, for whom miniatures were painted by the most skilful Indian artists. To date, Baburnama has been translated into more than 25 languages. The events of the work begin with the fact that the ruler becomes a 12-year-old little Babur. The work is told in the first person, and in it, in addition to what Babur saw in his life, he leaves interesting information about his battles, campaigns, cities and settlements that he reached. "Baburnoma" is autobiographical-it gives valuable information about the life of Babur, his contemporaries. Geography, cultural studies, and the art of that time even give an idea of the plant world[4].

The name of the author "Baburname" has already become famous and immortalized in the world. Thanks to our independence, Z. M. Babur returned to his homeland and to the people for centuries with all his status. His historical, scientific and literary heritage has become the spiritual heritage of our people. Uzbek scientists who worked on Boburnoma studied it historical, literally, geographically, translation and etymologically.“Boburnoma” was translated into

more than thirty languages of the world. Therefore there are some arguments about the translation development of the work. Our aim is to study and compare the cultural properties of proverbs in “Boburnoma” and reveal its adequate translation[2]. “Boburnoma” was translated by European scientists of oriental studies, such as: D. Vitsen, J. Leyden, W. Erskine, R. M. Caldecott, S.L. Poole, E. Holden, M. Elfinston, J. J. Lui, B. Grammon, and G. M. Eliot. V. Moreland, P. Kurteil, F. G. Talbot, A. Denison, A.S. Beveridge, H. Beveridge, H. Lamb, A. M. Shimmel. Russian scientists: N. I. Ilminskiy, N. N. Pantusov, V. V. Viyatkin, N. I. Vesedovskiy, V. V. Bartold, A. N. Samailovich, M. Salye, A. A. Semeyonov, A. Y. Yakubovskiy, I.V. Stebleva and Afghan scientists: Ahmad Ali Kohzod, Abdulhay Habibiy, Gulchin Maoniy, Indian scientists: Zokir Husayin, Nurul Khasan, Muni La’l, S. A. Sharmi, R. P. Tripatxi, P. Saran, Muhibul Khasan and others. During 1826–1985 “Boburnoma” was translated four times into English (1826, 1905, 1921, 1922) three times into French (1878, 1980, 1985) and only once into German. Among them there are such novels “Boburnoma”, which was written by Flora Ann Stealing (Paris, 1940), “Bobur” by Fernand Grenardning (Paris, 1930), “Bobur – the Tiger” by Harold Lamb (New York, 1980) by Vamber Gaskin. Russian and West European scientists such as Veselovskiy, Ilminskiy, Erskine, Eduard Holden, and Elfinston appreciated “Boburnoma”. Javaharlal Neru wrote in his book “Discovering India” about Bobur and Bobur’s generation’s influence on development of India and the world’s civilization. John Leyden and William Erskine made the first translation of “Boburnoma” in 1826. Annete Susannah Beveridge and Henry Beveridge translated it in 1921. The last and adequate version of translation of “Boburnoma” was made by the gifted translator and the author of “The Great Mughal Empire” Anna Maria Shimmel’s postgraduate Wheeler Thackston in 1996. Three translations were completed and now we can learn their versions through comparative analysis of original text with target texts. “According to Wh.Thackston’s point of view, S.Beveridge’s translation is the equivalent of students’ work, all the words of “Baburname” are

closely the same in dictionary, she tried to match Turkish (Uzbek) and English words in it. Professor Wh.Thackston published “Baburname”’s English translation in 1996. It was the third completed variant of the work, however this publication enriched the investigations of life, creativity and times of Babur[3].

The well-known orientalist M. Sale worked on the translation of "Boburnoma" for more than ten years, deeply studied the language of the work, tried to give the correct transcription of many terms, phrases and names. This translation opened up new opportunities for the popularization of "Boburnoma", the spread of its fame and the expansion of the scope of research on the work. But, despite all the painstaking work, there are inaccuracies and errors in this translation. For example, a number of names and names were given erroneously - "Kutlug'begim" became "Katakbegim", some words, such as "bukalamun", "torment" became incomprehensible. prof. N. Komilov notes that "there are still many ambiguities in Salier's translation" and writes that "the verses are given in prose translation and it is not indicated in what language they are written." This point is emphasized in another article. Other experts also noticed flaws in the Russian translation. Among other things, N. Dekhkanov writes¹ : “There are many inconsistencies in giving geographical names: instead of “Tarozkent”, “O'tror” is given, many historical cities are given distortedly in Russian: FanokatFinaket, etc.” Continuing his opinion, the author once again writes: “Such errors spoil the image of an “academic” publication, distort the language and content of the work ... if necessary, it must be retranslated to better comply with the Russian language. "In addition to the above errors, there are a number of other shortcomings. For example, in the 1993 edition, in a footnote on p. as "Bag-i Shimal". . In the 1993 edition, there is information about the earthquake in Kandahar on page 166. In the explanation given to him (p. 387), instead of "Kandahar" he is called "Agra" and s. k. The 1958 edition commented "Babur's handwriting": "It must be some kind of secret letter" (p. 455) says In the 1993

edition, the same explanation was given to this concept (in this edition it was changed to "Babur's Alphabet").

To sum up, we can proudly say that the works of our ancestors have their admirers even today, as they have gained power in history. Especially, the fact that the work has been translated several times into foreign languages proves that the work of Bobornama is perfectly written. Another point worth noting is that it is a very difficult process to preserve the original content of a work in the process of translation. This process requires great skill and knowledge from the author. It is impossible to translate the realities of nationality and culture, i.e. convey them in their own sense. Because every nation is rich in unique culture, mentality and national tradition. This shows how responsible and difficult a profession translation is.

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